

Original Article

Impact of Democratic Leadership on Employee Performance: A Moderated Medicated Analysis

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Abstract

Effective leadership plays a crucial role in shaping organizational outcomes, particularly in enhancing employee performance. Scholars and practitioners have extensively studied different leadership styles to understand their potential impact on various organizational dimensions, including job satisfaction, motivation, and productivity. The purpose of study is to investigate the effects of democratic leadership on employee performance and also the contextual factors that mediates the relationship between democratic leadership style and employee performance in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). The methodology used in this research is quantitative. For this research, the population is employees (individual) working in the SME's of Pakistan. A total 600 questionnaires were distributed among the selected population. Out of which 575 questionnaires were returned. 26 questionnaires were containing missing values. The final datasheet containing 549 fully completed questionnaires.

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Introduction

Leadership styles have been under the focus by various researchers to estimate their impact on employee performance (Baig et al., 2021). Sapta et al. (2021) describe leadership as motivating or encouraging people to complete tasks that help reach set objectives. Furthermore, Leadership is the act of influencing and guiding others toward accomplishing a common goal or vision (Northouse, 2018). Moreover, leadership is considered as vital factor in achieving organizational goals (Istikomah & Haryanto, 2020). According to Thanh et al., (2020) the circumstances in which leadership is practiced can also influence its effect on employee performance. Kouzes and Posner (2017) emphasized those leaders who establish trust and credibility within their teams foster greater engagement and enhance overall workforce performance. Furthermore, strong leadership can strengthen the productivity and performance of subordinates (SitiNurAisah, 2020). Democratic leadership style is associated with higher levels of employee satisfaction and engagement, as it brings up a sense of ownership and empowerment among employees (Hardian, 2015). Kim and Beehr (2018) stated that, giving autonomy is directly proportional to employees' loyalty and motivation that would uplift overall firms' productivity. Moreover, Babatunde (2015) added that having a strong connection between managers (leaders) and employees is key to achieving the company's goals.

This study aims to bridge the ongoing research gap by exploring how democratic leadership style influence employee performance in small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) sector. Given the pivotal impact of SMEs on economic growth and their challenges, ongoing research will anchor particularly on SMEs give deeper understanding relevant directly to this industry. So, Firstly, this study will investigate the direct impact of democratic leadership on employee performance. Secondly, explore the mediating role of perceived organizational support between them. Lastly, this research explores the moderating role of emotional intelligence between democratic leadership and employee performance. The research seeks to comprehensively understand

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organizational behaviour and leadership dynamics within the SME context. Adopting a holistic approach aims to offer valuable insights for scholars and practitioners in this field. Additionally, this research will help in formulating policies that encourage leadership adaptability, ensuring that businesses can navigate the complexities of the modern corporate environment while maintaining a productive and satisfied workforce.

This research offers significant contribution by giving insight into the field of leadership and organizational behavior, specifically focusing on Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Through a thorough analysis of democratic leadership style and their effect on employee performance, along with the inclusion of perceived organizational support as mediating variable, as well as emotional intelligence as a moderating variable, this research offers a detailed and insightful exploration of the various factors that influence employee performance. So, this study aims to answer below mentioned research question in SMEs sector by taking social cognitive theory as a theoretical framework.

1. How do democratic leadership influence employees' performance in SMEs?
2. How does perceived organizational support mediate the relationship between democratic leadership and employees' performance?
3. Does emotional intelligence moderate the relationship between democratic leadership and employees' performance?

Literature Review

The Theoretical Perspective of the Social Cognitive Theory

Social cognitions refer to the cognitive processes and structures (such as self-conceptions, standards, and goals) that people use to interpret events, plan actions, and regulate their motivation, emotions, and interpersonal behavior (Cervone, 1991). Research in social cognition has primarily explored how individuals perceive themselves and others in social contexts. Additionally, it has analyzed how people attribute causes to their own and others' behaviors, as well as the perceptual biases that shape these judgments. This model illustrates the SCT concept of reciprocal determinism, where leadership styles (environment), employee perceptions (cognitive factors), and their behaviors all interact dynamically to impact overall performance (Wood & Bandura, 1989).

Democratic leadership and Employee performance

Leadership style is a method of providing direction, executing plans, and inspiring individuals (Northouse, 2021). Northouse (2021) stated that for leaders to successfully manage their teams, it is crucial to identify the most suitable leadership style. In the business world, leadership is closely tied to performance, and effective leaders are those who can enhance their organization's success. In order to influence others, leaders carrying democratic leadership traits provide opportunities to work in collaboration with subordinates (Salsabila & Hetami, 2022). According to Kurniawan (2018) Democratic leaders enable employees to be more creative and innovative by providing them self-development. Cooperation and teamwork is the priority for democratic leaders in order to accomplish goals. They are always open for opinion, suggestion as well as criticism from their juniors (Salsabila & Hetami, 2022). Hence, we hypothesized that:

H1: Democratic leadership style has significant impact on employee performance.

Democratic Leadership and Perceived Organizational Support

Democratic leadership, which emphasizes participative decision-making and inclusive management practices, has a significant impact on perceived organizational support (POS). POS reflects employees' perception that their organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being (Alcover et al., 2018). However, Democratic leadership, by involving employees in decision-making processes, enhances their sense of ownership and commitment to the organization, leading to increased POS. According to Northouse (2018), democratic leadership involves sharing decision-making power with team members, which not only boosts employee engagement but also enhances their perception of being valued by the organization. Chung, and Sparrow (2005) highlight that effective communication practices, including providing clear information about organizational decisions, lead to a better comprehension of organizational goals and values, thereby enhancing POS. Robbins and Judge (2019) further emphasize that transparent communication and involvement in decision-making processes lead to a positive perception of organizational support. Hence, we hypothesized that:

H2: Democratic leadership style has a significant impact Perceived Organizational Support.

Perceived Organizational Support and Employee Performance

Perceived Organizational Support (POS) positively impacts various outcomes such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and performance. According to Warr (2002), when employees feel a strong sense of organizational support, they are more likely to exhibit positive behaviours, including a lower tendency to consider leaving their jobs. Whereas, Employees when feel unsupported by their organization, may engage in behaviours aimed at avoiding work or even deviant actions stated by Omar et al., (2011). They might develop a dislike for their jobs and consider leaving the organization (Dawley et al., 2010). Rhoades and Eisenberger, as cited by Arshadi and Hayavi (2013), suggest that POS (Perceived Organizational Support) represents how an organization views its employees. When an organization demonstrates that it values employees' dedication and loyalty as a sign of their commitment, employees, in turn, become more aware of and responsive to the organization's commitment to them. However, Organizational commitment describes the level at which employees share and support the organization's objectives and their inclination to remain with the company (Marthis & Jackson, 2009). Moreover, according to Maan, (2020) POS enhance job satisfaction, employee dedication and their performance. Hence, we hypothesized that:

H3: Perceived organizational Support has a significant impacts employees' performance.

Mediating Role of Perceived Organizational Support between Democratic Leadership and Employee Performance

The concept of democratic leadership, introduced by White and Lippitt in the 1960s, highlights the importance of leaders promoting active group participation in decision-making (Choi, 2007). A key feature of this leadership style is the leader's practice of seeking input from members when establishing goals, plans, and policies (Tengilimoğlu, 2005). According to the literature, organizations that employ democratic leadership tend to achieve better production performance and higher employee satisfaction over time compared to those led by other leadership styles says Robbins and Coulter (2012); Lunenburg and Ornstein (2013). When employees feel that their organization genuinely values their well-being, they are more likely to contribute to the company's success (Kim et al., 2016). POS serves as an indicator of a company's intentions to support and care for its employees. Whereas Previous studies indicate that perceived organizational support (POS) significantly influences the relationships between job design, career development, and performance (Cheng & Yang, 2018). It enhances employees' capacity to manage their job responsibilities says Kurtessis et al., (2017). Additionally, a high level of POS fosters better collaboration, productivity, and communication among colleagues, often resulting in increased cooperation (Erdogan& Bauer, 2009). Hence, we hypothesized that:

H4: Perceived organizational support mediates the relationship between Democratic leadership and employees' performance.

Moderating Role of Emotional Intelligence between Democratic Leadership and Employee Performance

Emotional Intelligence (EI), as conceptualized by Goleman (1995), refers to the ability of individuals to recognize, understand, and manage their own emotions as well as those of others. Democratic leadership involves actively engaging subordinates or followers in the decision-making and implementation processes. This approach boosts job satisfaction and supports the development of team members' skills (Bhatti et al., 2012). According to Goleman (2020) Effective leaders inspire individuals to achieve peak performance by connecting with their emotions while managing their own feelings. Leading and executing tasks becomes particularly challenging in projects with strict deadlines. However, leaders who cultivate their emotional intelligence can foster harmony in their relationships and demonstrate empathy in all interactions, says Goleman (2020). Moreover, according to Humphrey (2002), a leader's capabilities can significantly influence the emotional atmosphere within a group. Also, Leadership can evoke strong emotions, as noted by Goleman (1995). It is primarily a process of managing emotions, where leaders not only regulate their own feelings but also influence the emotions of their followers (Yukl, 2002). In their study, Sy et al., (2005) explored how emotional intelligence among employees and their managers relates to job satisfaction and performance. Their findings indicated that employees with higher emotional intelligence experienced greater job satisfaction and performance levels. Furthermore, they discovered that a manager's emotional intelligence positively impacted job satisfaction more significantly for employees with lower emotional intelligence compared to those with higher emotional intelligence. Hence, we hypothesized that:

H5: Emotional intelligence moderates the direct relationship between Democratic leadership and employees' performance.

Methodology

Sample and Data Collection

For current study, the target population is the employees (individual) working in SME's of Pakistan. A total 600 questionnaires were distributed among the selected population. Out of which 575 questionnaires were returned. 26 questionnaires were containing missing values. The final datasheet containing 549 fully completed questionnaires.

Measurement

The research questionnaire contain 50 items are a divided into 4 parts. Democratic leadership contains 11 items, employee performance contains 7 items, perceived organizational support contains 8 items and emotional intelligence contains 24 items. The researcher has used five point Likert scale. The scale range goes from strongly disagree to Strongly Agree.

Demographic

The sample of the research consists of 64.0 % male. 30.0% employees having age between 31-40 years. 32.7% employees having 4-6 years working experience and 32.5% employees are intermediate.

Table 1

Demographic

Demographic Variables	Category	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	356	64.0
	Female	193	36.0
Age	21 - 30	81	14.7
	31 - 40	166	30.2
	41 - 50	128	23.3
	51 - 60	148	27
	Above 60	32	5.8
	Less than 1 year	106	19.3
Experience	1 – 3	125	22.7
	4 – 6	180	32.7
	7 – 10	86	15.6
	Above 10 years	52	9.4
Education	Diploma	146	26.5
	Matric	126	22.9
	Intermediate	180	32.5
	Graduate	165	30.0
	Postgraduate	32	5.9

Results

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Democratic Leadership	4.32			
Perceived Organizational Support	4.17	0.778	-0.787	0.109
Employee Performance	4.21	0.762	-0.723	0.111
Emotional Intelligence	4.28			

The descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis) of Democratic leadership, perceived organizational support, employee performance and emotional intelligence are shown in table 2.

Measurement Model

Procedure containing two stages i.e. measurement model and structural model are performed in PLS-SEM. In stage one, measurement model analysis, outer loadings, reliability validity are observed.

Step-1 Estimate Factor Loading with Significance

Outer loadings of variables are discussed below:

Assessment of Outer Loadings

The exogenous composite construct of the research is democratic leadership (DL), perceived organizational support (POS), employee performance (EP) and emotional intelligence (EI). DL measure eleven items i.e. DL_1, DL_2, DL_3, DL_4, DL_5, DL_6, DL_7, DL_8, DL_9, DL_10, DL_11, POS measure eight items i.e. POS_1, POS_2, POS_3, POS_4, POS_5, POS_6, POS_7, POS_8, EP measure seven items i.e. EP_1, EP_2, EP_3, EP_4, EP_5, EP_6, EP_7 and EI measure twenty-four items i.e. RM_1, RM_2, RM_3, RM_4, RM_5, RM_6, RM_7, SA_1, SA_2, SA_3, SA_4, SELFA_1, SELFA_2, SELFA_3, SELFA_4, SELFA_5, SM_1, SM_2, SM_3, SM_4, SM_5, SM_6, SM_7, SM_8. The outer loadings of all variables are above 0.70 and significant. The range is 0.702-0.793, 0.795-0.708, 0.725-0.793 and 0.706-0.784 respectively. The values are demonstrated in table 3.

Table 3

Outer Loadings

	DL	EI	EP	POS
DL1	0.734			
DL10	0.762			
DL11	0.793			
DL2	0.752			
DL3	0.702			
DL4	0.791			
DL5	0.725			
DL6	0.762			
DL7	0.715			
DL8	0.727			
DL9	0.714			
EP1			0.725	
EP2			0.729	
EP3			0.786	
EP4			0.734	
EP5			0.738	
EP6			0.729	
EP7			0.793	
POS1				0.769
POS2				0.711
POS3				0.795
POS4				0.708
POS5				0.775
POS6				0.787
POS7				0.733
POS8				0.751
RM1		0.737		
RM2		0.777		

	DL	EI	EP	POS
RM3		0.723		
RM4		0.741		
RM5		0.741		
RM6		0.784		
RM7		0.772		
SA1		0.779		
SA2		0.783		
SA3		0.713		
SA4		0.729		
SELFA1		0.777		
SELFA2		0.734		
SELFA3		0.785		
SELFA4		0.708		
SELFA5		0.707		
SM1		0.739		
SM2		0.706		
SM3		0.773		
SM4		0.782		
SM5		0.777		
SM6		0.769		
SM7		0.765		
SM8		0.724		

Step 2: Reliability Analysis

Cronbach Alpha

The acceptable threshold for Cronbach alpha is ≥ 0.70 (Nunnally&Bernstein, 2010; Kline, 2016) while Hair et al. (2011) recommended that ≥ 0.60 is also acceptable. Table 4 demonstrated the Cronbach alpha that all constructs have above the mark alpha scores. It shows good reliability variables over time.

Composite reliability

Resultant value of composite reliability above 0.95 represent that individual indicators are measuring the same concept that is not acceptable (Hair et al., 2020). Table 4 demonstrated the composite reliability results and all constructs have above the mark composite reliability scores. It shows all variables have good reliability over time.

Table 4

Reliability and Validity

Latent Variables	Cronbach Alpha	CR	AVE	Discriminant Validity
1. Democratic Leadership	0.895	0.898	0.501	Yes
2. Perceived Organizational Support	0.865	0.867	0.514	Yes
3. Employee Performance	0.832	0.836	0.510	Yes
4. Emotional Intelligence	0.953	0.953	0.501	Yes

Step-3 Validity Analysis

Hair et al. (2017) recommended two major types of validity analysis to test the measurement model (i.e. convergent validity and discriminates validity).

Convergent Validity

The acceptance value of AVE is 0.50 and above. The value 0.50 or above denote that this construct explained variance is more than 50%. Table 4 demonstrated the AVE scores and all constructs have above the mark AVE scores. It shows all variables have good validity.

Discriminates Validity

Evaluation of discriminant validity can be derived through three metrics i.e. cross loadings, Fornell-Larcker method (Fornell&Larcker, 1981), and heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) (Henseler et al., 2015).

Fornell-Larcker Discriminant Validity Analysis

The diagonal values demonstrated in Table 5 show square root of AVE. All diagonal values are greater than its respective correlation scores. It shows all variables have good discriminant validity as per Fornell-Larcker method.

Table 5

Fornell-Larcker Discriminant

	DL	EI	EP	POS
DL	0.7			
EI	0.829	0.694		
EP	0.848	0.807	0.706	
POS	0.82	0.839	0.804	0.717

Heterotrait-Monotrait Discriminant Validity Analysis

Table 6 demonstrated the HTMT scores and all constructs HTMT scores do not cross the limit i.e. HTMT_{0.95}. It shows all variables have good discriminant validity as per HTMT ratio method.

Table 6

Heterotrait-Monotrait Discriminant

	DL	EI	EP	POS	EI x DL
DL					
EI	0.893				
EP	0.871	0.898			
POS	0.833	0.824	0.844		
EI x DL	0.472	0.439	0.397	0.412	

Cross Loadings Discriminant Validity Analysis

Table 7 demonstrated that all constructs cross loadings are higher than the respective cross loadings in the row. It shows all variables have good discriminant validity as per cross loadings method.

Structure Model

Step-1 Multicollinearity analysis

Results in table 8 reveals that there is no issue collinearity in the data as all values of VIF is less than 3 as per the threshold of Hair et al. (2020).

Table 7

Multicollinearity

	VIF
DL1	1.972
DL10	2.151
DL11	1.465
DL2	2.036
DL3	1.808

	VIF
DL4	1.741
DL5	1.81
DL6	1.606
DL7	1.483
DL8	1.915
DL9	1.889
EP1	1.589
EP2	1.545
EP3	1.731
EP4	1.62
EP5	1.726
EP6	1.812
EP7	1.63
POS1	1.61
POS2	1.729
POS3	1.581
POS4	1.629
POS5	1.631
POS6	2.074
POS7	1.884
POS8	1.917
RM1	2.512
RM2	2.188
RM3	2.233
RM4	2.343
RM5	2.546
RM6	1.961
RM7	2.048
SA1	2.712
SA2	2.128
SA3	2.29
SA4	2.37
SELFA1	1.35
SELFA2	2.447
SELFA3	2.822
SELFA4	2.374
SELFA5	2.332
SM1	1.691
SM2	2.164
SM3	2.412
SM4	2.063
SM5	1.994
SM6	2.067
SM7	2.12
SM8	2.484
EI x DL	1

Step-2 Evaluate Size and Significance of Path Coefficients

Structural model relationship estimates are obtained that represent the path coefficients that show the hypothesized relationship between study variables. The coefficient values of PLS path model represent the ordinary least square

regression beta coefficients (β) (Ringle et al., 2018). The estimated value of standardized regression coefficient (β) depict the relationship among the independent variable and dependent variable on the condition that estimated p-score is statistically significant for standardized regression coefficient (β) (Anderson, Babin, Black, & Hair, 2014). The standardized value of path coefficients falls between -1 and +1. The resultant value of path coefficient closes to +1 represent strong positive relationship while the value of path coefficient closes to -1 represent strong negative relationship that are usually significant. When the value of coefficient is near to 0 that show weaker relationship. The value that is very close to 0 is usually insignificant. The understanding of path coefficient is described as how much change is liable in endogenous construct due to change in exogenous construct with ± 1 standard deviation (Henseler et al., 2017).

Figure 1

Table 8
Direct Path

Direct Path	Beta Value	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
DL -> EP	0.491	8.008	0
DL -> POS	0.82	35.945	0
POS -> EP	0.225	3.814	0

The direct effects represent the one to one relationship among the variables.

H1: Democratic leadership style has significant impact on employee performance.

It was hypothesized that democratic leadership has an impact on employee performance. As shown in the table, $\beta = 0.491$, $t = 8.008$, $p = 0$. These results showed that β value is positive and shows the size of path, t value above ± 1.96 i.e. 8.008, and p value is less than 0.05 which show significance of the path.

H2: Democratic leadership style has a significant impact Perceived Organizational Support.

It was hypothesized that democratic leadership has an impact on perceived organizational support. As shown in the table, $\beta = 0.82$, $t = 35.945$, $p = 0$. These results showed that β value is positive and shows the size of path, t value above ± 1.96 i.e. 35.945, and p value is less than 0.05 which show significance of the path.

H3: Perceived organizational Support has a significant impacts employees' performance.

It was hypothesized that perceived organizational support has an impact on employee performance. As shown in the table, $\beta = 0.225$, $t = 3.814$, $p = 0$. These results showed that β value is positive and shows the size of path, t value above ± 1.96 i.e. 3.814, and p value is less than 0.05 which show significance of the path.

Step-3 Examination of Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Tables 9 represents the R² scores of variables i.e. employee performance and perceived organizational support. The R² value for employee performance is 0.810 which is considered substantial, the R² value for employee taking charge behavior is 0.467 which is considered substantial.

Table 9

Coefficient of R-square

Construct	R-square	R-square adjusted
Employee performance	0.810	0.812
Perceived organizational support	0.467	0.463

Step-4 Examination of Effect Size f²

The threshold of effect size (f²) is 0.02 for small effect, 0.15 for moderate effect, and 0.35 for large effect (Chin, 1998a; Cohen, 1988). Table 11 demonstrates the f² scores of exogenous variables i.e. democratic leadership, emotional intelligence and perceived organizational support. All exogenous variables have large effect size with employee's performance.

Table 10

Effect Size f²

Constructs	EP	POS
DL	0.310	0.027
EI	0.005	
POS	0.014	
EI x DL	0.005	

Mediation Effects

H4: Perceived organizational support mediates the relationship between Democratic leadership and employees' performance.

It is hypothesized that Perceived organizational support mediates between democratic leadership and employee performance. As demonstrated in the table 12, $\beta = 0.185$, $t = 3.713$, $p = 0$. The results shows that perceived organizational support mediates between democratic leadership and employee performance.

Table 11

Indirect Effects

Indirect Effect	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
DL -> POS-> EP	0.185	3.713	0

Moderation Effects

H5: Emotional intelligence moderates the direct relationship between Democratic leadership and employees' performance.

It was hypothesized that Emotional intelligence moderate's relationship between democratic leadership and employee's performance. As demonstrated in the table 13, $\beta = 0.027$, $t = 1.456$, $p = 0.001$. These results showed that β value is positive and shows the size of path, t value above ± 1.96 i.e. 1.456, and p value is less than 0.05 which show significance of the path.

Table 12

Moderation Effects

Moderation Effects	Beta Value	T Value	P values
EI x DL -> EP	0.027	1.456	0.001

Discussion and Conclusion

Structural equation modeling is employed to assess the suitability of the proposed model and validate the significance of relationships among observed and latent variables. H1 posits a connection between Democratic leadership and employee performance. The results show significant positive relationship between democratic leadership and employee performance, as reflected by the statistical value of $\beta = .491$ ($p < 0.000$). Thus, the interpretation of the results indicates that Democratic leadership have a positive and significant impact on the employee performance. The current study's findings are consistent with previous research conducted by Elenkov (2002), which also demonstrated that Democratic leadership has a positive and significant influence on the employee performance. H2 posits a connection between Democratic leadership and perceived organizational support. The results show significant positive relationship between democratic leadership and perceived organizational support, as reflected by the statistical value of $\beta = .82$ ($p < 0.000$). Thus, the interpretation of the results indicates that Democratic leadership have a positive and significant impact on the perceived organizational support. The current study's findings are consistent with previous research conducted by Eisenberger et al., (2020), which also demonstrated that Democratic leadership has a positive and significant influence on the perceived organizational support. H3 posits a connection between perceived organizational support and employee performance. The results show significant positive relationship between perceived organizational support and employee performance., as reflected by the statistical value of $\beta = .225$ ($p < 0.000$). Thus, the interpretation of the results indicates that perceived organizational support have a positive and significant impact on the employee performance. H4 posits mediating relationship of perceived organizational support between democratic leadership and employee performance. The results show significant positive mediating relationship perceived organizational support between democratic leadership and employee performance, as reflected by the statistical value of $\beta = 0.185$, $t = 3.713$, $p = 0$. Thus, the interpretation of the results indicates that perceived organizational support mediates the relationship between democratic leadership and employee performance. Hypothesis 5 (H5) proposes the moderating relationship of Emotional intelligence between democratic leadership and employee's performance. The results reveal that Emotional intelligence moderates the relationship between democratic leadership and employees' performance, as reflected by the statistical value of $\beta = 0.027$, $t = 1.456$, $p = 0$. Thus, the interpretation of the results indicates that Emotional intelligence moderates the relationship between democratic leadership and employees' performance.

Implication of Study

Theoretical Implications

This study offers some interesting theoretical insights by looking into how democratic leadership impact employee performance, emotional intelligence (EI) and perceived organizational support (POS). By comparing democratic leadership, the research builds on Bass's Transformational Leadership Theory, highlighting how democratic leadership can foster proactive behavior and trust among employees (Bass, 1990). Additionally, it emphasizes the crucial role of EI in these relationships, aligning with Goleman's Emotional Intelligence Theory, which underscores the importance of leaders' emotional capabilities in creating supportive work environments (Goleman, 1995). POS serve as key mediating variable, in this context, POS aligns with organizational support theory, showing how perceived support can foster trust and commitment among employees (Eisenberger et al., 1986). Focusing on SMEs, this research fills a gap in leadership studies, offering valuable insights into how leadership practices impact employee performance in resource-limited environments. This interdisciplinary approach enhances our understanding of leadership, emotional intelligence, and organizational behavior, ultimately improving employee outcomes.

Social Contribution

This study underscores the pivotal role of effective leadership in SMEs, crucial for driving economic growth and job creation. However, it showcases how democratic leadership, underpinned by emotional intelligence, can significantly boost employee performance by enhancing engagement, innovation, and organizational support. Moreover, by focusing on perceived organizational support, the research offers valuable insights into fostering positive work environments where employees feel valued and empowered. These findings highlight ways to promote job stability, innovation, and improve the competitiveness of SMEs, thereby contributing to broader societal goals of economic and social development.

The Contribution to Policy

This study provides valuable insights for policy development in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), with a focus on leadership style, emotional intelligence, employee performance, and the impact of perceived organizational support. Policymakers can utilize these findings to develop leadership programs that emphasize democratic leadership, which is associated with higher levels of employee performance and satisfaction. Prioritizing emotional intelligence training for leaders is crucial, as it enhances the relationship between leadership and performance by fostering better interpersonal relationships and organizational outcomes. Furthermore, implementing policies that create a supportive work environment, where employees feel valued and empowered to take initiative, can drive innovation and improve performance. Emphasizing perceived organizational support through transparent communication and career development opportunities can enhance employee engagement and retention. These policy recommendations aim to help SMEs boost productivity, foster employee creativity, and ensure sustainable long-term growth.

Limitations and Further Direction

This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the sample is confined to SMEs, which limits the ability to generalize the findings to larger organizations or different sectors. The use of a cross-sectional design also restricts the ability to establish causal relationships between the variables. Additionally, self-report bias may affect the accuracy of measures for emotional intelligence and perceived organizational support. Cultural differences could also influence the interaction between emotional intelligence and leadership style and the concept of perceived organizational support may not fully capture all factors that impact performance. To address these limitations, future research could employ a longitudinal design and include a broader range of organizations, such as larger firms, to assess the varying impact of leadership across different contexts.

Conclusion

In summary, this study explored the effect of democratic leadership on employee performance in SMEs, with emotional intelligence acting as a moderator and perceived organizational support as mediators. The results indicate that democratic leadership enhances employee performance by increasing perceived organizational support. Emotional intelligence further amplifies this effect. Overall, democratic leadership, bolstered by emotional intelligence, proves to be more effective in improving employee performance within SMEs.

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